

Spectral and Structural study of the complexes of first Row transition Metal Cu (II) with Schiff Base

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Abstract

Coordination compounds and Schiff base compounds in presence of coordination chemistry mechanism for Schiff base for mation explain the basicity character of the Schiff base ligands, biological important of Schiff base ligands and the biological revolution of transition metals using copper, for complexation of Schiff base ligands. Diversity applications of Schiff bases complexes due to catalytic biological application such anti bacterial, anti fungal, anti oxidant, anti inflammetry, anti-viral, anti tumor etc. In Cu(II) complex with the new Schiff bases of the type p-HABT and p-HBAMP were prepared by reaction of p-hydroxy benzaldehyde with 2 amino thiazole / 2 amino -6 methyl pyridine have been synthesized and characterized with the help of IR and electronic spectral data. Comparative bacterial behaviour of Schiff bases with their Cu(II) complexes have also been studied against E. coli and S Aureus.

Keywords Cu(II), p-hydroxy benzaldehyde, 2 amino thiazole / 2 amino -6 methyl Pyridine.

Introduction

The first imines were prepared in the nineteenth century by a classical method that involves condensation of a carbonyl compound with the help of amine under the distillation of a zeotropic and to remove water formed in the system, molecular sieves are used. The Ligands are derived from the condensation reaction of aldehydes and primary amines[1]. They are also know as anils, azomethines imines, aldimine, ketamines etc.

Where R and R' maybe hydrogen and R'' may be aromatic or non aromatic or may be the same or different.

Aim of study

Metal chelates of Schiff bases have played a central role in the development of coordination chemistry. They are also important components of every day products as varied as cleaning material, medicines, inks and paints. Several Schiff base are reported to be therapeutically active possessing cytotoxic, anti-inflammatory and antiviral activities.

Review of Literature

Schiff base metal complexes is their biological activity with the main aim being the discovery of safe and effective therapeutic agents for the treatment of bacterial infectious and cancers. A number of Schiff base metal complexes have a diverse spectrum of biological and pharmaceutical activities. For instance transition metal complexes of Schiff base ligands bearing "O" and "N" donor atoms are very important because of their biological proper lies such as antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory [2], analgesic [3,4] anticonvulsant [5], anti-tubercular [6], antioxidant [7] and anthelmintic [8]. The Schiff base-transition metal complexes have also been used as biological models to understand the structure of bimolecules and biological processes [9].

v. Elemental analysis data (in %) $C_{10}H_8N_2OS$ (204.15) found C=57.95% H=3.97% N=13.80%, S=15.75%

vi. Calculated : C = 58.82% H=3.92% N = 13.72% S = 15.70%.

vii. IR Frequencies : $\nu-OH = 3629\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu\text{ CH=N} = 597\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu\text{ C-S-C} = 837\text{ cm}^{-1}$

(b) Schiff base derived from p-Hydroxy benzaliden with 2-amino-6-methyl pyridine (SB₂)

The Schiff base was prepared by refluxing calculated quantities of 1.22gm of p-hydroxy benzaldehyde in ethanol was mixed with ethanolic solution of 1 ml of 2-amino-6-methyl pyridene (which is dissolved in ethanol). The mixture was refluxed for 12 hours over a water bath. The solution containing the product was allowed to cool at room temperature. The excess of ethanol was distilled off and the concentration solution was cooled in refrigerator for 24 hours the obtained product was filtered and washed with acetone several time and followed by ether. It was recrystallized with absolute alcohol and dried under reduced pressure of $CaCl_2$.

i. Molecular formula = $C_{13}H_{12}N_2O$

ii. Molecular weight = 212.21

iii. Melting Point = $170^{\circ}C$

iv. Colour = Light yellow

v. Elemental analysis (in %) found C = 72.45%, H = 5.52%, N = 13.25%

vi. Calculated C = 73.57, H = 45.69, N = 13.19%

vii. Important IR frequencies – $\nu-OH = 3630\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu\text{-CH=N}=1612\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu\text{ C-N-C} = 1498\text{ cm}^{-1}$

1.3 Synthesis of metal complexes

(a) Preparation of metal complexes with p-HBAT (SB₁)

Where : M = Cu (II), X = Cl⁻

Synthesis of the Schiff Base Metal (II) complexes

The Schiff base metal (II) complexes were prepared by reacting the Schiff base with the metal (II) ions a per the literature method (II)

The metal chloride (5m mol, 25ml) dissolved in ethanol or distilled water was added drop wise to a solution of SB₁ or SB₂ (10m ml, 25ml) in the solvent. The resulting mixture was stirred for 30 minutes and refluxed for 2-3 hours on a water bath. The contents were cooled and solvent was slowly evaporated and washed with ethanol, ether and dried in air.

Cu(C₁₀H₈N₂OS)₂Cl₂ : MP = 155⁰C, Formula weight = 542.74, colour = Dirty Black μ (B.H.) = 1.80% of element found C = 45.57%, H = 2.88%, N = 10.25%, S=11.75%, Cl = 13.25%, M = 11.76%

Calculated C = 44.26%, H=2.95%, N=10.32% S= 11.81%, Cl = 13.06%, M=11.71%

IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) $\nu_{(CH=N)}$ =1602, ν_{C-S-C} (thiazol) = 837, $\nu_{(C=N)}$ = 1512

Coordination Modes : ν_{M-O} = 515, ν_{M-N} = 420, ν_{M-Cl} = 294.

Cu(C₁₃H₁₂N₂O)₂Cl₂ : MP = 160⁰C Formula weight = 558.86 colour = Dark brown, μ = 1.75 of element found C = 01.56%, H = 4.45%, N = 10.10%, Cl = 12.72%, M = 11.47%

Calculated : C = 0.558%, H = 4.33%, N = 10.02%, Cl = 12.68%, M = 11.36%

IR Frequencies : $\nu_{(CH=N)}$ =1600, ν_{C-N-C} (thiazol) = 1513, $\nu_{(C=N)}$ = 1512

Coordination Modes : $\nu_{(M-O)}$ = 525, $\nu_{(M-N)}$ Pyridine = 423.

1.4 Biological Assay

Schiff bases are characterized by an imine group-N=CH, which help to clarify the mechanism of transamination and racemization reaction in biological system [11].

The synthesized ligand and its transition metal (II) complexes were screened in vitro for their antibacterial activities against *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterial strains using filter paper disc method [12, 13]. The disc diffusion method was used because of its convenience, efficiency and low cost.

The activity of newly synthesized Schiff base ligand is also lesser than that of its complexes. The comparative antimicrobial evaluation reveals that the Schiff base $C_{10}H_8N_2OS$ is almost inactive against *E. coli* at the concentration of 250ppm and 500ppm, while it showed optimum at 750ppm. The activity of Cu(II) complexes increase with 750ppm and less active in 250ppm.

$C_{13}H_{12}N_2O$ is almost in active against *S. aureus* at the cone of 250ppm and 500ppm while it showed optimum activity at 750ppm in less than *E.coli*. Cu(II) complexes of this ligand is less active.

Table-1

Antibacterial Activity Data Against E.Coli

(inhibition of radial growth in mm)

S. No.	Compounds	Concentration (ppm)		
		250	500	750
1	Ethyl alcohol	-	-	-
	DMF	-	-	-
2	$C_{10}H_8N_2OS$	-	-	4.2
3	$Cu(C_{10}H_8N_2OS)_2Cl_2$	4.2	6.0	8.0

Table-2

Antibacterial Activity Data Against S. Aureus

(inhibition of radial growth in mm)

S. No.	Compounds	Concentration (ppm)		
		250	500	750
1	Ethyl alcohol	-	-	-
	DMF	-	-	-
2	$C_{10}H_8N_2OS$	-	-	4.1
3	$Cu(C_{10}H_8N_2OS)_2Cl_2$	4.2	5.0	7.0

Antimicrobials-antibiotics, anti-virals anti-fungal and anti parasitics are substances widely used to prevent and treat infections in humans, aquaculture, livestock and crop production. Their effectiveness is now in jeopardy because a number of antimicrobial treatments that once worked no longer do so because microorganisms have become resistant to them.

Microorganisms that develop resistance to commonly used antimicrobials are referred to as super bugs. UNEP released in 2023 the flag ship report Bracing for Super bugs, strengthening environmental action in the 'One Health' response to antimicrobials resistance.

Microscope creatures, which have been around for and over 3.8 billion years, have the greatest genetic and metabolic variety. They play crucial function in ensuring.

1.5 Electron spin resonance values of Cu(II) complexes (cm^{-1})

Parameter	Complexes	
	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{OS})_2\text{Cl}_2$	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2$
g	2.07	2.07
g^\wedge	2.09	2.09
$g^{\wedge\wedge}$	2.17	2.13
g_{av}	2.11	2.10
G	1.88	1.44
A^\wedge	24	28
$A^{\wedge\wedge}$	144	192
A_{av}	64	82.6
D^\wedge	18928	18927
$D^{\wedge\wedge}$	39689	51996.86
I/D^\wedge	0.043	0.044
$I/D^{\wedge\wedge}$	0.0209	0.0159
μ_{eff}	1.83	1.81

Result and Discussion

1.6 IR spectral Analysis

(a) The IR ligand band at 1597cm^{-1} shifted to higher side in the complexes ($1597\pm 20\text{cm}^{-1}$) suggesting participation of azomethine group in complexation [14]. Medium intensity band at $\sim 410\text{-}424\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes are assignable to ν M-N stretching vibration [15] which confirm the involvement of Nitrogen atom of azomethine group in the coordination. In the spectrum of Ligand a broad band of ν -OH stretching vibration appear at 3629cm^{-1} , which disappeared in complexes thus indicating deprotonation of phenolic oxygen. The involvement of Phenolate oxygen in the coordination is also supported by the band appearing at $513\text{-}520\text{cm}^{-1}$ due to M-O [16].

The characteristic infra-red bands in the spectra of the ligand are observed at ~ 1512 (C=N cyclic) ~ 1377 (C-N) and $\sim 837\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-S-C) of the thiazole moiety [17]. In halogen bands were identified in the region $300\text{-}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with certainty.

(b) The strong absorption band for the pyridine ring occurring at 1498 cm^{-1} (ν -pyridine) is shifted to higher frequency region by $15\text{-}20\text{cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating the participation of nitrogen atom of pyridine in the coordination [18]. In the far infrared region $410\text{-}425\text{cm}^{-1}$ due to M-N bond [19, 20].

In the infrared spectra of the ligand, the broad band at 3630 cm^{-1} phenolic (OH) [21] disappears in the spectra of all the complexes indicating the disappears in the spectra of all the complexes indicating the deprotonation of phenolic-OH group and coordination to the metal in through the oxygen atom which is further substantiated by hypso chromatic shift of the phenolic $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ modes around 1480 cm^{-1} of free ligand by

10-20 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes. The coordination through phenolate oxygen of the ligand is further confirmed by the occurrence of new bands at 520-512 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes which may be assigned to M-O [22] stretching vibration respectively. The infrared spectra of Schiff base ligand exhibits a sharp band at 1612 cm^{-1} due to the presence of azomethine group [23] which is shifted to lower frequency region by 20-40 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating the coordination of (-C=N), nitrogen in complexation. This is further confirmed by the appearance of new bands at 520-510 cm^{-1} due to M-N bond respectively.

(ii) Mass spectral studies

The main characteristic of a molecule when exposed to high energy electrons is the initial formation of molecular ion with a high degree of vibrational and probably electronic excitation. The majority of M^+ ions would fragment in such a way that the distribution of smaller amount of energy would occur more rapidly.

Conclusion

The mass spectra of the two Schiff bases derived from p-hydroxy benzaldehyde with 2-aminothiazole / 2-amino-6-methyl pyridine were recorded at room temperature. A graphic presentation of spectrum is used for determination of molecular mass of Schiff bases.

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